

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

TURKISH ORIGIN WORDS IN THE SLAVIC LANGUAGES

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Abstract

The role of Turkic languages in the enrichment of the lexicon of Slavic languages is great. There are thousands of words of Turkish origin in Russian. The root words created by Turkish words form the definite part of the lexical fund of the Russian language. The components of these root word slots are subject to the grammatical, semantic and functional laws of the Russian language and enrich it. These words were not only developed independently in the Russian language, but also created their own root word slots and phraseological units. The components included in the root word slots created by morphemes of Turkish origin are widespread in the toponyms, hydronyms and anthroponyms of the Russian language. Some archaic semantic shades of the Turkish origin words are still preserved in Russian toponyms. This article deals with the Turkish origin onomastic units, which are widely used in Russian, and their semantic functional features.

Keywords: root word slots, turkisms, antroponyms, toponyms, hydronyms, onomastic units.

Introduction

The relationships between Russian and Turkish have been known since ancient times. It is necessary to note several periods in the history of Russian-Turkish language relations. The oldest period dates back to the first years of our era, before the establishment of the Kyiv-Russian state.

From the 6th to the 7th centuries AD, the Slavs entered into trade relations with the Turkic Avars, the Volga Bulgars, the Caspians, and other Turkic peoples. From ancient times, the settlement of Turkic and Slavic peoples in neighboring territories, trade relations forced the representatives of these peoples to learn each other's language.

The directions of these very broad relations are also interesting for their breadth and diversity. Russian culture benefited from the Turks, borrowing clothing, weapons, songs and tales, military structure and way of thinking.

The words of Turkish origin were included in the dictionary of modern and ancient Russian, "Slove o polku Igoreve", "Zadonshchina", "Domostroy" and others. It has been preserved in literary monuments and chronicles. The famous Russian linguist N.K.Dmitriyev considered all words included in Slavic from Turkish, regardless of their origins, to be Turkism.

According to V.Arakin, regardless of their previous history, words that passed into Slavic languages through Turkic languages are considered Turkisms. Thus, words related to religion, law, and everyday life that passed from Mongolian, Iranian, Arabic, and other languages were considered Turkisms by researchers.

There is a qualitative advantage in Turkish borrowings in the Russian language, which is the antiquity of Turkish borrowings. Due to the density and antiquity of ties in Russian-Turkish relations, Russians, who were under Turkish influence, adopted not only the customs and traditions of the Turks, but also various

aspects of the Turkic-Tatar way of life. They even became close to this people from a spiritual point of view, familiarizing themselves with and adopting their language. So many words and expressions have passed from Turkic languages to Russian that these lexical units have become so close to the words of the Russian language that it is currently difficult to replace a large part of them with special words and expressions in Russian.

The extensive connection between the Slavic and Turkic languages has been so continuous and consistent in the history of the mutual relations of these peoples that, as a result, it has left deep traces in the lexicon, phraseology, phonetics and grammar of the Russian language and in the onomastics.

Toponyms

Great Russian scientist A.K. Matveyev in his dictionary "Geographical names of the Urals. Short toponymic dictionary" divides the word "aktay" into the components "ak" and "tay". He explains the word "ak" in the meaning of color, and the lexeme "tay" in the meaning of "mountain" and "baby horse". In our opinion, this is a wrong idea. "Ak tay" should be translated as "white river, like a white watery, clear, transparent, watery river". The name of one of the left tributaries of the Yalva River in the Yekaterinburg region is Agyar. This name is formed from the words "ag" - high, upper and "yar" - abyss, ravine. The word "ag" in the expression "ag yar" means "high", "upper".

In the toponyms of Western Siberia, the expressions Akkaya, akkoba, Ak khorum (mountain, mountain) are often found. In the languages of the Siberian Turks: Khakass, Tuva, this word, found in the forms "korum", "khorem", "khorum", refers to stony, rocky areas formed on mountain slopes. "Ak korum" means high slope; "ak kaya" means high rock; "ak kobu" means high plain. N. Kononov, in his article "On the semantics of the words "kare" and "ak" in Turkic

geographical terminology,” notes that the adjective “kara” has many meanings in Turkic languages.

The archaic shades of meaning of the word “kara” (black) have been preserved more in the toponymic layer, unlike other layers of the lexical composition of the language.

Kartalı – Karatalı, Chelyabinsk Oblast, Russian Federation – a city located on the Ayat River. The word “Kara” is used in the meaning of color. Karatay, Karatash – a mountain called in Bashkiria. In these homonyms, it is used in the meanings of “big”, “giant”. The name of the city of Krasnoyarsk in the Russian Federation is derived from the words Kizil Yar. There is a Kiziltash road in the Irtysh region of the Russian Federation.

The railway station “Kizler” near Rostov consists of a set of the formants Kizil + er, meaning “red place”. It is so called because the soil in this settlement consists of red rocks.

Hidronyms

Karachaykul – the name of a lake in the Chelyabinsk Oblast, Russian Federation. In the Bashkir and Tatar languages, karachay means pine tree. From this we can conclude that this hydronym means “pine lake”. The term “Aksu” is also widely used in the hydronyms of the territories inhabited by Turkic-speaking peoples. M.F. Rozen in his dictionary “Dictionary of Geographical Terms of Western Siberia” uses the word “ağ” in three meanings. In the first meaning, it refers to white, transparent waters that originate from glaciers; in the second meaning, it refers to waters with a constant flow; and in the third meaning, it refers to rivers that flow heavily and do not dry up in summer.

Karatıbs – a lake in the Chelyabinsk region of the Russian Federation. In ancient Turkic monuments, “tabır”, “teriz” mean a salty area. The water of this lake is indeed very salty. Karabash – the name of a city in the north of the Chelyabinsk region of the Russian Federation. Karabashka – the name of a river in the Chelyabinsk region. Karabash – a settlement in the Bogulma district of Tatarstan. Karamaskalı – the name of a village in Bashkiria. Karabashka – the name of a river in the Chelyabinsk region.

Antroponyms

Russian surnames containing roots of Turkic origin are of particular importance. The Turkic elements included in the semantic structure of these surnames prove that Russian-Turkic language relations began in ancient times. The components included in the nests of root words of Turkic origin are very widely used in the composition of Russian surnames.

The surname Karamazov was formed from the words “kara” – “kara” and мазать (to smear), that is, from a combination of Turkic and Russian lexemes. The surname Karaulov was formed in the Russian language by adding the suffix - “ов” to the forms “караул” - “гаровул” that came from the Turkic languages. Another noble surname, which is considered one of the Russian anthroponyms, is Karacharov. This surname was formed on the basis of

the toponyms “kara dzar” – “kara yar” – “kara yer”. Among the surnames in Russian that have the word “kara” – “kara” in their structural composition, the onomastic units Karamazov and Karaulov can be cited.

The Russian surname Karachinsky is also of Turkic origin. The members of this noble family loyally served the Russian Empire and the Tsarist throne. N.A. Baskakov notes that the surname Karachinsky comes from the Crimean Tatar word gypsy. This title was once given by the Crimean Khan to the nobles who served the kingdom. In modern Turkic languages and ancient Turkic, there is a rich root word nest of the word “Garaja”. In these nests, the word “garaja” is mainly used in the meaning of “karayanız”.

The surname of the famous Russian writer and historian Nikolai Karamzin is also of Turkic origin. This surname consists of the components Kara Mirza - Qara Mirza, and was transferred to the Russian language from the Crimean Tatar language. Mirza, of Kara-Turkic origin, is a combination of the words amir (prince) of Arabic origin and zade (son) of Persian origin. The word “kara” - “qara” included in this surname is one of the most frequently used lexical units in Turkic languages.

The Russian princely surname “Kurakin” (Kurakin) derives its origin from the word “Kuraka”. Here, the basis of the word is the Turkic root guraq (dry) and the Russian suffix -a. The etymology of this word includes the word “kurghaq”. This lexeme had a very rich root paradigm in the ancient Turkic language: kurghaq (dry); kurgha (drying); gurghiz (drying); guri (drying); kurıǵlıǵ (infertile, childless, barren); kurıǵu (drying, drying); gurin (drying); guriz (drying); gurit (drying); kurü (drying); kurüg (dry); kurügla (drying); kurüǵlan (dried); kurüǵluq (drought, dryness); kurüǵsi (drying).

Conclusion

Turkic-speaking peoples are settled in the territories where they have historically lived. These territories mainly cover a large area, including a certain part of the Asian continent, the south-east of Europe, the North Caucasus, Transcaucasia, and South Azerbaijan.

The Turkic peoples had a great position in the cultural and ethnic composition of Russia. The ideological and cultural life, language, and even political struggle of this state for many years can be fully and objectively understood in the context of Turkish-Russian relations. The establishment of Russia's relations with the Middle East and the Turkic world gave impetus to the development of Slavic and Turkic language relations. The settlement of Turkic and Slavic peoples in neighboring territories and trade relations developed relations between these peoples.

As a result of long-term economic, political, and territorial contacts, a common lexicon of the Russian and Turkic peoples was formed. Russian-Turkic relations and relations are reflected in ethnography and culture, architecture and ornaments, household items and customs, many details of everyday life, as well as in the vocabulary of the Russian language, in Russian chronicles and the “Slove o polku İgoreve”, in terms of

animal husbandry and hunting, in surnames and nicknames, toponyms, hydronyms, and a huge number of Turkic borrowings preserved in all semantic groups of the Russian language, terminology and onomastic system. The study of the ethnography and onomastics of the history of the Turkic world, which is connected with a single root, is one of the most urgent problems. In our study, we discussed the semantic functional characteristics of onomastic units of Turkic origin, which are widely used in the Russian language.

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